

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS TO BE AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

OPERAS Final Technical Design

DELIVERABLE 5.6

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS TO BE AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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TERMINOLOGY

CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
COESO	Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues (EU project)
EA	OPERAS Executive Assembly
GA	OPERAS General Assembly
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
IMS	Integrated Management System
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PRISM	Peer Review Information Service for Monographs
SAC	Scientific Advisory Committee
SIG	Special Interest Group
SMS	Service Management System
SPM	Service Portfolio Management
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STB	OPERAS Services and Technology Board
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VERA	Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation

Abstract

This document offers an updated comprehensive overview of the OPERAS portfolio of services, summarising the development activities and key components utilised or integrated within the portfolio. It highlights the diverse range of services offered and their significance in covering the social sciences and humanities (SSH) research landscape, and how they are managed. Though this is the final report of the OPERAS-PLUS project, the service portfolio and the services will continue to evolve.

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Executive summary

This deliverable (D5.6 “OPERAS Final Technical Design”) presents the final consolidation of OPERAS’ technical and service design, produced at the close of the OPERAS-PLUS project. It captures the maturity of the OPERAS Service Portfolio and its operating model, confirming OPERAS’ readiness for long-term sustainability and integration as a European Research Infrastructure.

By the end of the project, the OPERAS service portfolio has reached a high level of maturity, with most services in production and others progressing through advanced development stages. Core services such as GoTriple, Metrics, VERA, Pathfinder, PRISM, Hypotheses, together with internal components including OPERAS ID, FitSM training and the OPERAS messaging environment, are now delivered as a coherent and stable offer. This marks the definitive shift from project-based pilots to a functioning, production-level infrastructure.

The report also demonstrates how OPERAS has embedded professional service management practices. FitSM has been adopted as the common reference framework, implemented through an Integrated Management System and complemented by supporting tools (Confluence, Jira Service Management, GitLab/GitHub). These measures provide consistency, traceability, and quality assurance across the distributed infrastructure, with alignment to ISO 9000 certification planned.

The technical design described here underpins OPERAS’ broader transition. It secures operational resilience, enables continuous improvement, and ensures interoperability across services and communities. Most importantly, it positions OPERAS to sustain its service offer beyond the lifetime of OPERAS-PLUS, with national contributions and central budgeting as the foundation for the forthcoming transition to ERIC.

In summary, D5.6 establishes OPERAS’ technical baseline for the future: a complete and production-ready service portfolio, a professional service management system, and a sustainability model robust enough to carry OPERAS into its next phase as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium.

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1. Introduction

OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of social sciences and humanities (SSH) research.

This document offers a final overview of the current OPERAS portfolio of services, summarising the development activities and key components utilised or integrated within the portfolio. It highlights the diverse range of services offered and their significance in covering the SSH research landscape. A final report will be delivered at M36.

Terminology used follows the FitSM® lightweight service management standard¹, specifically FitSM-0, which provides a common vocabulary used by the other parts of the standard (in particular by FitSM-1) and as the IT Service Management approach being adopted by OPERAS.

Several of the services supported by the OPERAS-PLUS project have their own dedicated deliverables providing further details, namely D5.2 “Metrics Service”, D5.3 “Pathfinder”, D5.4 “PRISM”, D5.5 “Translation Design Study”.

Therefore, this document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: introduces the document and its structure.
- Section 2: provides an overview of the current OPERAS service portfolio
- Section 3: details the development activities over the last 18 months including information on future activities
- Section 4: offers the underlying service management approach and progress on implementation with usage examples
- Section 5: concludes the overall document.

¹ www.fitsm.eu

2. Current Service Portfolio Overview

OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research.

OPERAS offers a range of services that greatly benefit researchers and authors in the SSH community. These services enable researchers to discover open scholarly resources, improve the quality of peer-review practices, engage in collaborative citizen science projects, and more.

There are three types of services provided by OPERAS:

1. **Managed:** Services managed by OPERAS, responsible for overall coordination, delivery and evolution.
2. **Community:** Services managed directly by community providers but discoverable through the OPERAS catalogue. These services are required to have sustainable structures to be established but receive direct OPERAS participation, contribution and support.
3. **Internal:** Services necessary for managing and operating the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, both technical and non-technical.

These services are grouped into eight categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Multilingualism, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.

2.1. OPERAS Service Catalogue

Figure 1: OPERAS Service Catalog

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The current service catalogue is provided below:

1. [GoTriple](#): Enables users to discover and reuse open scholarly resources in multiple languages. It also allows users to connect with other authors and researchers in the humanities and social sciences and provides innovative tools such as visualisation, analytics, web annotation, trust building and recommender systems.
2. [Pathfinder](#): Enhances the visibility of editorial services and guides editors, editorial managers and authors to discover the best service to fit their needs.
3. [Metrics](#): Collects usage and impact metrics from various sources related to published Open Access books, which can be accessed, displayed and analysed from a centralised database.
4. [VERA](#): Allows SSH researchers to build citizen science projects together with diverse stakeholders and provides tools to facilitate collaboration and project development.
5. [Hypothèses](#): Provides a space for SSH research blogs, fostering innovative formats of scholarly communication and offering multilingual content.
6. [PRISM](#): Aims to improve transparency and trust in Open Access book publishing by providing standardised information about the peer-review process.

There are other services in various stages of development that may be included in the OPERAS service catalogue in future. One example is [Mondaecus](#), a platform to provide a collaborative environment for researchers and professionals to translate and edit scientific documents in multiple languages, which is currently at the beta stage and in the process of being integrated into the OPERAS Service Catalogue. Similarly, the OPERAS Innovation Lab is planned to be added to the Service Catalogue at the end of 2025 as a service.

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Figure 1: OPERAS Services and Research Lifecycle

2.2. OPERAS Internal Services

OPERAS ID

Messaging

Internal services include:

1. FitSM²: a training and certification program in lightweight service management mainly for OPERAS members.
2. OPERAS ID³: provides a single solution for user registration across all services, offering federated identity such as ORCID, Google, EGI Check-in.
3. Messaging⁴: dedicated Mattermost server for collaborative messaging.

In addition to these core services, OPERAS also offers a range of professional services to support the management and coordination of scholarly communication in the SSH. This includes consultancy services on topics such as FAIR data management, IT service management (ITSM), policy development, and Open Science. OPERAS also provides

² www.fitsm.eu

³ <https://id.operas-eu.org>

⁴ <https://mattermost.com/>

communication and outreach services to help increase the visibility and impact of SSH research.

As a legal entity, OPERAS ensures the sustainability and long-term development of its services while aiming to improve the quality and efficiency of scholarly communication in SSH.

3. Service Development

3.1. Service Phases

There are a number of different approaches and methodologies to describing the lifecycle of services. The following table summarises the naming conventions and descriptions for each, as well as the equivalent Technology Readiness Level (TRL) that OPERAS has adopted.

Service Phase	Definition	TRL Equivalent
Evaluation	Early-stage discussions and documentation regarding a specific opportunity	1–2
Design	Approved service starting the design and development of the service	3–4
Alpha	Prototype available and testing in limited scale ongoing	5–6
Beta	Version available for wider scale testing	7
Production	Feature complete version with majority of service management aspects defined	8–9
Discontinued	Service no longer available for new customers, but still available for legacy users	--
Retired	Service no longer available and no longer being used by anyone	--

Table 1: Service Phases

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL)

TRLs are a method of estimating the technology maturity of components during the acquisition process. For non-technical components, you can specify “n/a”. For technical

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components, you can select them based on the following definition from the EC:

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
- TRL 5 – technology validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in an operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies).

3.2. Service Roadmap

The OPERAS service roadmap tracks the current status of the various services, as well as the timing of key milestones, mainly for planned service phase changes. This view helps to link to the communications teams for preparing relevant messages. It also maps to the projects and funding sources that are supporting the development.

This strategic overview is crucial as many of the OPERAS services are spread across almost all service phases with varying timings as well.

Service	Status	Type	Category	2022				2023				2024				2025				Funding Source
				Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4													
GoTriple	Production	Managed	Discovery																	TRIPLE
Metrics	Production	Managed	Analytics																	OPERAS-PLUS
VERA	Production	Managed	Research4Society																	COESO
Pathfinder	Production	Managed	Discovery																	OPERAS-PLUS
Fiscal Hosting	Beta	Managed	Professional																	OPERAS AISBL
Innovation Lab	Beta	Managed	Collaboration																	OPERAS-PLUS
Hypotheses	Production	Community	Research4Society																	OpenEdition
PRISM	Production	Community	Quality Assurance																	OPERAS-PLUS
Mondaecus	Beta	Community	Multilingualism																	OPERAS-PLUS
FITSM Training	Production	Internal	Training																	OPERAS, Projects, Fees
Messaging (Mattermost)	Production	Internal	Collaboration																	COESO, OPERAS-PLUS
OPERAS ID (AAI)	Production	Internal	Operations																	OPERAS AISBL

Figure 2: OPERAS Service Roadmap Overview

At the start of 2022, there were only 4 services in Beta, with 6 services either in the

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design phase or earlier. Therefore, it was a busy year from a development perspective. By mid-2023, 5 services were in production, 3 in Beta, 2 in Alpha and 1 still under design. By Q3 2025, 9 services are in production, and 3 in Beta. The following table provides an overview of the service phase changes for each service.

Service	Q1 2022	Q3 2023	Q3 2025
GoTriple	Beta	Production	Production
Metrics	Beta	Beta	Production
VERA	Design	Beta	Production
Pathfinder	Design	Beta	Production
Hypotheses	Production	Production	Production
Fiscal Hosting	N/A	Alpha	Beta
PRISM	Beta	Production	Production
Mondeacus	Design	Design	Beta
Innovation Lab	N/A	Design	Beta
FitSM Training	N/A	Production	Production
Messaging	N/A	Production	Production
OPERAS ID	N/A	Beta	Production

Table 2: Service Phase Changes

3.3. Future Development

3.3.1. Sustainability

2025 is a critical year for OPERAS, as shown in the service roadmap because the majority of services are in the production phase. This requires not only a focus on continual service improvement and dissemination, but on sustainability as well.

Through the legal entity, OPERAS AISBL ensures the sustainability and long-term development of its activities and services, as well as the effective collaboration and coordination of its members and partners. The AISBL status also enables OPERAS to

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engage in partnerships and collaborations with other organisations and stakeholders and to represent the interests of the SSH research community at the European and international levels.

As OPERAS is transitioning towards becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), current financial and sustainability planning is being defined. Active collaboration is ongoing to ensure that all services are taken into consideration, both current and future. A cost analysis was refined as part of the ESFRI questionnaire update, which is helping to understand total costs and forecasting and is currently being discussed as part of the OPERAS Board of Governing Representatives (BGR). The aim is to have the operation and maintenance of the services covered by the central budget paid by the individual member states. Community services will continue to be provided as in-kind by the individual providers, with the added-value services provided by OPERAS central hub (i.e. dissemination and service management support).

OPERAS is also participating in a number of EC-funded projects. To ensure organisational, technical and financial sustainability, projects aim to identify Key Exploitable Results (KER) with legal and administrative options that can provide the long-term sustainability of each KER. While projects offer an important pathway, sustainability strategies need to be coordinated across a variety of projects and activities and should aim for diversification.

The OPERAS service portfolio is transitioning from project-based development towards a model of permanent operational management, anchored by the adoption of FitSM practices for lightweight service management and quality assurance. As explained above, with OPERAS moving towards the establishment of an ERIC, national contributions are foreseen as a future mechanism to strengthen the long-term operational base. In parallel, OPERAS is exploring additional sustainability avenues aligned with the principles of public mission support. Potential approaches under consideration include value-added services, freemium models, white-label adaptations, and enhanced project-based collaborations, always respecting the fundamental commitment to open scholarly communication and public good provision. New projects such as GRAPHIA, LUMEN, and FASCA are already contributing with practical use cases, technical enhancements, and additional resources to reinforce the service ecosystem, with further opportunities being pursued through upcoming funding calls.

OPERAS is exploring a diversified strategy that combines public funding, collaborative project frameworks, institutional engagement (financial and in-kind support), and operational efficiencies to ensure resilience, adaptability, and service continuity across its distributed infrastructure.

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3.3.2. Service Usage and KPIs

Service usage and key performance indicators (KPIs) are crucial components in evaluating the effectiveness and impact of a service. Service usage pertains to the extent to which a service is utilised by its intended audience, encompassing metrics such as the number of users, frequency of usage and the specific features accessed. Monitoring service usage can provide insights into user engagement and the service's overall value to the target audience.

OPERAS deploys a mix of collection mechanisms comprising tools such as Matomo/Mixpanel as well as manual collection on a monthly basis (reviewed during each Services and Technology Board - STB), extracting key information from local databases. During each STB, KPIs are reviewed and additional intelligence is extracted, such as usage behaviour.

In 2025, as the majority of services are reaching higher levels of maturity, more focus is being put on usage statistics, which are also included in the monitoring dashboard to be delivered at the end of the project.

3.3.3. Potential Opportunities

OPERAS Innovation Lab

A Work Package (WP4) of the OPERAS-PLUS project was dedicated to establishing the OPERAS Innovation Lab to stimulate ideation and potentially prototyping of innovations for the SSH community. Building on recommendations from the Future of Scholarly Communication report (OPERAS-P)⁵, the Lab is positioned as OPERAS' central knowledge hub for innovation. It acts as an interface between OPERAS members, industry, e-infrastructure providers, and the wider Open Science community, providing guidance to stakeholders and facilitating collaboration for innovative and FAIR outputs.

The Innovation Lab focuses on building a permanent, embedded innovation capacity within OPERAS, coordinating across multiple projects, while also developing activities beyond project frameworks. It develops repeatable, adaptable methodologies and procedures that can be applied across services and contexts, making innovation a sustained and scalable part of OPERAS' work.

The Innovation Lab also contributes to OPERAS' long-term viability by diversifying funding sources and revenue streams and fostering collaborations that can include partnerships with industry, targeted innovation funding and other suitable mechanisms. This approach ensures that the Lab's outcomes not only generate

⁵ <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4746>

meaningful impact for the SSH community but also remain adaptable over time, in line with OPERAS mission as a public Research Infrastructure.

OPERAS Innovation Fund

The purpose of the OPERAS Innovation Fund will be to support innovative projects that align with OPERAS' vision, mission and values, including community projects.

In so doing, it is intended to enhance the capacity of OPERAS to quickly assess, fund and scale open-source solutions that have been developed either by publicly funded research organisations or by private companies and to adapt or integrate them into OPERAS Research Infrastructure to better support Open Access, Open Science and Open Innovation in Europe. The OPERAS Innovation Fund supports the generation of open-source, public goods that address the most pressing challenges in Open Scholarly Communication, with a special emphasis on Social Sciences and Humanities to the broadest extent of the concept.

As such, the OPERAS Innovation Fund is not intended to provide continuing support for ongoing research projects/programs or to serve as a substitute for national or European funding. The OPERAS Innovation Fund is a fund intended to seed innovative interdisciplinary research, and it will be very intimately articulated with the OPERAS Innovation Lab.

The creation and constitution of the fund will be analysed and prepared during the transition period towards the ERIC creation.

Pricing Schemes for Individual Services

Applying pricing schemes to individual services isn't as straightforward in the academic and research space as in private industry, especially in areas such as open access, where there are higher expectations that services are offered free at the point of delivery. However, in order to add flexibility in how the OPERAS services are sustained, continued exploration of applicable pricing schemes will be conducted. It is expected to initially focus on two popular pricing models that work well with a continually available free option: the "freemium" model, where only premium features or enhanced functionalities have a fee; and membership, offering exclusive benefits and rewards to members who pay a recurring fee.

It is also important to recognise that numerous other schemes exist, each with its unique benefits and drawbacks that will not be discounted entirely, just potentially not an initial focus, e.g. one-time purchase, usage-based, amongst many others.

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Applying pricing schemes to individual services requires thoughtful consideration of the target audience, the unique value proposition of the service, and the overall strategic objectives. While freemium and membership fees are powerful pricing models, other strategies should be explored to find the right fit for the specific service and customer/user group.

4. Service Management

4.1. Reference Standards

Using management standards offers numerous benefits. Some of the key advantages include:

- **Improved Efficiency:** Structured frameworks and best practices that help streamline processes, reducing inefficiencies and optimising resource utilisation.
- **Enhanced Quality:** Ensure consistent quality in products and services, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.
- **Risk Reduction:** Identify and mitigate potential risks to enhance overall resilience.
- **Compliance and Regulation:** Meet legal and regulatory requirements, reducing the risk of penalties and legal issues.
- **Recognition:** Gain credibility and increase partnerships.
- **Competitive Advantage:** Differentiate from competitors, showing commitment to excellence and continuous improvement.
- **Cost Savings:** Through improved efficiency, reduced waste and better resource management.
- **Customer Trust and Confidence:** Build trust with customers and stakeholders, as it demonstrates a commitment to quality and reliability.
- **Consistency in Operations:** Provide a common language and set of practices, promoting consistency in operations across different departments or locations.
- **Continuous Improvement Culture:** Emphasise a culture of continuous improvement, encourage seeking ongoing advancements in processes and performance.
- **Employee Engagement and Satisfaction:** Boost employee engagement and job satisfaction by reducing ambiguity and promoting a sense of accomplishment.
- **Easier Collaboration and Integration:** When multiple organisations adopt the same standards, it facilitates collaboration and integration in supply chains and partnerships.

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Overall, management standards offer a systematic and proven approach to organisational management, enabling organisations to drive excellence, meet customer expectations and navigate complex environments effectively.

4.1.1. ISO 9000 – Quality Management

ISO 9000 is an internationally recognised set of standards for quality management systems. ISO 9000 provides a comprehensive framework that organisations can follow to ensure consistent and high-quality products and services, ultimately leading to enhanced customer satisfaction and continuous improvement.

Developed and maintained by the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), ISO 9000 is applicable to any organisation of any size and industry. Its principles focus on customer focus, process efficiency and a commitment to meeting regulatory and legal requirements.

The aim is for OPERAS to achieve formal certification by 2028, immediately after its transition to becoming an ERIC.

4.1.2. FitSM – IT Service Management

IT Service Management is a discipline that helps provide services with a focus on customer needs and in a professional manner. It is widely used in the commercial and public sectors to manage IT services of all types, but current solutions are very heavyweight with high barriers to entry.

FitSM is an open, lightweight standard for professionally managing services. It brings order and traceability to a complex area and provides simple, practical support in getting started with ITSM. FitSM training and certification provide crucial help in delivering services and improving their management. It provides a common conceptual and process model, sets out straightforward and realistic requirements and links them to supporting materials.

Through FitSM, the aim is to conduct effective IT service management in the federated environment and achieve a baseline level of ITSM, which can also act in support of ‘management interoperability’ in federated environments (e.g., EOSC). It is also compatible with other ITSM standards such as ISO/IEC 20000 and can be seen as complementary to ISO 9000.

In addition, FitSM offers an opportunity to receive a formal certification backed by the certification authority, APMG International, for anyone successfully passing exams,

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which is offered at multiple levels: Foundation, Advanced and Expert.

The aim is for OPERAS to achieve a formal certification by 2027 as it transitions towards becoming an ERIC. Implementation has already started.

Service Portfolio Management	DONE
Service Level Management	IN PROGRESS
Service Reporting	NOT STARTED
Service Availability and Continuity Management	NOT STARTED
Capacity Management	NOT STARTED
Information Security Management	IN PROGRESS
Customer Relationship Mgmt.	IN PROGRESS
Supplier Relationship Management	DONE
Incident and Service Request Mgmt.	DONE
Problem Management	IN PROGRESS
Configuration Management	DONE
Change Management	DONE
Release and Deployment Mgmt.	SET-UP
Continual Service Improvement	SET-UP

Figure 3: OPERAS IT Service Management System implementation status⁶

4.2. Service Governance

The Services and Technology Board (STB) is responsible for managing the portfolio of services and associated technologies regarding OPERAS AISBL and OPERAS federated services. This includes all services that are planned, live or to be retired/discontinued. The STB conducts regularly scheduled service reviews. It also collects inputs from other relevant groups or leaders, such as EA, GA, OCT, SIGs, SAC, etc., for research community needs and the evolution of technology.

⁶ Full process descriptions available at: <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/748/?tmstv=1692808999>

Governance Structure

Figure 4: OPERAS Governance Structure

Responsibilities include:

- Advise OPERAS management on the priorities for evolving the service portfolio
- Conduct regularly scheduled service reviews with service owners
- Maintain a service strategy and implement the recommendations from the OPERAS GA, EA, OCT and SIGs
- Steer the creation, review and approval of service design and transition packages, including descriptions and specifications alongside any information to be added to the service portfolio
- Ensure that major changes to services and solutions are endorsed by the process managers/owners
- Obtain approval from the relevant governance bodies for all new services and services to be discontinued

The Board is governed by the OPERAS General Assembly through the OPERAS Executive Assembly to investigate any activity within its Terms of Reference.

The STB holds regular monthly meetings.

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4.3. Support Tools

OPERAS offers/uses three supporting tools for the information, project and service management:

Confluence

Collaborative information management system to share knowledge efficiently, capture requirements and assign tasks

Jira Service Management

Helpdesk for external user communication and general ticketing system (incidents, bugs, improvement suggestions, etc.)

GitLab

An open source end-to-end software development platform with built-in version control, issue tracking, code review, continuous integration (CI) / continuous delivery (CD), etc.

4.3.1. Confluence

Offered by Atlassian, Confluence⁷ is a collaborative workspace software platform that enables teams to create, organise and share content, fostering seamless collaboration and knowledge sharing within organisations.

OPERAS uses Confluence as its Integrated Management System (IMS), as well as offers it to projects, such as OPERAS-PLUS. An IMS is a set of processes, tools and technologies designed to efficiently collect, store, organise, retrieve and disseminate information within an organisation or a specific context.

⁷ <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>

The screenshot shows the OPERAS Confluence frontpage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Confluence' and various menu items like 'Home', 'Recent', 'Spaces', 'Teams', 'Apps', and 'Templates'. A search bar is located on the right. The left sidebar contains a tree view of the space's content, with 'Service Portfolio Management (SPM)' currently selected. The main content area features the OPERAS logo, a subtitle 'open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities', and a 'Welcome to the OPERAS Integrated Management System' section. Below this, there is a paragraph explaining the purpose of the IMS and another paragraph detailing its basis on the FitSM Standard and ISO 9000. The page also includes a search bar for articles, sections for 'Most viewed articles' and 'Recently updated', and a 'Quickstart' button.

Figure 5: Screenshot of OPERAS Confluence Frontpage

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Figure 6: Screenshot of OPERAS-PLUS Project Confluence Frontpage

4.3.2. JIRA

Jira is a project management and issue tracking software also developed by Atlassian. It allows teams to plan, track and manage projects and tasks efficiently, facilitating collaboration, workflow automation and real-time reporting.

Specifically, OPERAS uses its Jira Service Management⁸ product as a true helpdesk, because it provides an additional functionality to communicate directly with external users who aren't only licensed users.

The widget has been embedded on all webpages of managed services, where users can submit tickets directly.

First implemented in Oct 2022, a total of 210 tickets have been submitted at the time of writing (Aug 2025) with 164 of them resolved/closed (~78%).

4.3.3. GitLab and GitHub

GitLab is a web-based DevOps platform that provides a complete set of tools for version control, continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD), code review and issue

⁸ <https://www.atlassian.com/software/jira/service-management>

tracking. It allows software development teams to collaborate effectively, manage repositories, automate the software delivery process and track project progress in a single integrated environment.

GitHub is a web-based platform and version control system that enables developers to collaborate on software projects and track changes to their codebase. It provides a central repository for storing and managing source code, allowing developers to work together, review code and manage software releases efficiently. GitHub's features include issue tracking, pull requests, continuous integration and seamless integration with various development tools, making it a popular and powerful platform for software development and open-source projects.

As many of the OPERAS services were developed via different projects and different project teams over the years, the tools used were also selected on an individual basis. One activity moving forward will be to see how to harmonise the different approaches in order to have a more coherent and consistent approach to how OPERAS services are managed from a technical development perspective. Below are 2 examples of the TRIPLE project using GitLab and the Metrics service using GitHub. Additionally, the OPERAS ID development initially used the TRIPLE project GitLab space. One improvement would be to shift development areas as part of an OPERAS umbrella with individual services having dedicated spaces under it.

Figure 7: Screenshot of GoTriple GitLab space

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Figure 8: Screenshot of Metrics GitHub space

5. Conclusions and Next Steps

A key achievement outlined in this document is the substantial maturation of OPERAS' services. The majority of services have transitioned into the production phase. As we move forward, we are shifting our focus towards dissemination and sustainability. This transition brings about exciting opportunities for growth and expansion as well as challenges, particularly in ensuring the long-term sustainability of our initiatives.

As OPERAS transitions towards becoming an ERIC, national contributions from member states are a key factor to ensure the operation and maintenance of core services. To guarantee resilience, adaptability, and service continuity, OPERAS is exploring a diversified sustainability strategy that combines public funding, collaborative project frameworks, institutional engagement, operational efficiencies, and the investigation of potential value-added services, freemium models, and white-label adaptations.

Beyond sustainability, OPERAS is actively pursuing new opportunities for growth and innovation. The OPERAS Innovation Lab, established through the OPERAS-PLUS project, is set to become a knowledge hub for stimulating ideation and prototyping innovative solutions for the SSH community, with the potential to generate additional

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revenue streams. Complementing this is the proposed OPERAS Innovation Fund, designed to quickly assess, fund, and scale open-source solutions that align with OPERAS' vision and address pressing challenges in Open Scholarly Communication.

Through these strategic advancements in service development, sustainability planning, and innovation initiatives, OPERAS demonstrates a commitment to enhancing the quality, accessibility, and community ownership of SSH research. The continuous evolution of its service portfolio, coupled with the adoption of rigorous service management standards like FitSM and aspirations for ISO 9000 certification, underscores OPERAS's dedication to efficiency, quality, and long-term impact, ensuring it remains responsive to the evolving needs of the SSH scholarly landscape.

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